

Next Steps

Socio-cultural, gender, and legal experts from B2-InF are currently analyzing all the information collected during the project's first phase. This consists of a content analysis of both the interviews done with the young population (18-30 years of age) and the information provided by the leading ART clinics in the 8 European sample countries (Spain, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, Kosovo, Albania, Macedonia, Slovenia).

This analysis will provide the necessary information for the elaboration of 8 national recommendation guidelines that will aim to guide all stakeholders involved in ART (mainly industry, scientific associations and governments) to a fundamental improvement of the information offered to society and align their practice with the expectations, concerns and knowledge of the young population.

After the first elaboration of the guidelines, we will have an internal workshop to discuss the drafts. Then, we will have a validation workshop to validate the guidelines, involving all the stakeholders. After that, the project's third and final stage will consist of strategic dissemination of the guidelines.

